

**BIKO.ID : OPTIMIZING THE POTENTIAL OF COCOA BEANS TO
INTEGRATED THE DIGITAL ECONOMY BASED AND COCOA
INDUSTRY IN INDONESIA
(CASE STUDY OF COCOA FARMERS IN LOMBOK)**

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Abstract

Cocoa is a plantation commodity whose role is quite important for the national economy, especially as a provider of employment, sources of income and foreign exchange. In addition, cocoa contributes 9% to GDP. On the other hand, there are fundamental problems to date that have not been resolved, especially those faced by farmers, namely that there is still asymmetric information that makes farmers' income maximum productivity. Asymmetric information about the price of cocoa has resulted in a lack of farmers' income, in addition, there is still a lack of MSME players in managing cocoa beans because of lack of adequate capital (machinery, production costs) is a major problem in the development of the cocoa industry in Indonesia. The purpose of this research is to optimize the rapid development of technology to increase the income of farmers and business people in the cocoa industry through the optimization of the role of BIKO.id. Biko.id serves to facilitate farmers in marketing and to attract investors to invest in order to facilitate the financing of MSME processing from cocoa beans. Biko.id also functions to make it easier for MSME players to get raw materials (cocoa beans) to be processed into packaging forms (dry snacks, powder, etc.), especially for domestic farmers. This paper is a literature study that is presented descriptively and is supported by several kinds of literature that have a lot of relevance to the problem under study. In addition, it is combined with face-to-face relationship (In-depth Interview) data to study objects. Data processing techniques were carried out by descriptive analysis and Critical Factors Success (CFS) analysis. Of course, in the application, some support is needed from various parties, including investors, academics, practitioners, governments so that the implications can arise by sustainability. Through the optimization of SMES pplications or websites.

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1. Introduction

One of the most developed agricultural business sectors in Indonesia is Cocoa. Indonesia has an area of cacao plantations recorded at 1.4 million hectares with a production of approximately 500 thousand tons each year, placing Indonesia as the world's third largest producer country after Ivory Coast (Ivory Coast) and Ghana. Ivory Coast, with an area of 1.6 Ha and production of 1.3 million tons per year and Ghana of 900 thousand tons per year. So it is natural that Indonesia is said to be one of the main cocoa producing countries in the world. (Bappenas.2016). Cocoa Is one of the plantation commodities whose role is quite important for the national economy, especially as a provider of employment, income sources and foreign exchange. The proof is in 2015, the agricultural sector including cocoa contributes 9% to Gross Domestic Product (GDP). (PerkebunanNews.2015).The potential for cocoa development in Indonesia is very promising if managed properly starting from cultivation, post-harvest, processing industry, packaging to distribution and marketing processes. (Supristiwendi. 2017). the proof of its production during the period 1980-2016 (Estimated Figures), Indonesian cocoa production also fluctuated and

tended to increase. In 1980 Indonesian cocoa production amounted to 10,284 tons than in 2015 amounted to 661,243 tons or an average increase of 13.99% annually. From the estimation results of the Directorate General of Plantation, 2016 cocoa production will increase by 15.00% compared to 2015. The highest production during the period 1980-2016 occurred in 2010 which amounted to 837,918 tons. In the 2012-2016 period or over the past five years, the average growth of cocoa production increased by 1.63% every year. However, the increase in cocoa production was not followed by an increase in the income of cocoa farmers. One of the farmers and cocoa work in the hamlet in Senara, North Lombok Regency which has the potential to work cocoa and the cocoa processing industry as well as cocoa village tours with Kampung Coklat Senara. the chocolate village as the main container for the economic drive of the senara community, precisely Senara Hamlet, Bentek Village, Gangga District, North Lombok, NTB. Kampung Coklat Senara has a lot of potential natural resources that are unique and suitable to be developed into nature such as cocoa, an area of 1 hectare of cocoa, waterfall tours, and good natural attractions developed, campsites, stalls that provide plantation produce cocoa which can be used to help produce cocoa and fermented cocoa beans.

However, there are still found some obstacles in the development of the chocolate village in order to increase the income of the people in the company, among others: Not yet optimal Availability of Support Chocolate village tourism attractions like 1) Lodging (Homestay) that has not been optimally optimized. Besides That, The Most Important Constraints Are 2) Not Considered by Structural Planning either in terms of Marketing of Tourism Villages and Plantation Products. Problems of Structural Planning in terms of Marketing Include: a) Promotion of Cocoa Beans that have not yet been processed and which are still traditional, that is, relying on promotion from mouth to mouth and maximally maximized natural tourism. While the constraints of the cocoa bean system where b) access to capital for farmers to process cocoa beans which are various products and to support tourism are still not optimal. c) there are still limited partnerships between cocoa industry entrepreneurs and cocoa plantation farmers. d) trading system of cocoa beans that are still long (dominated by middlemen). Of the problems above, the main problem faced by the chocolate village is the marketing of cocoa beans. If the marketing of cocoa beans is not successful, all efforts are in vain, in other words, the production costs are not met. This problem is often faced by farmers where the price of their agricultural products is very low and even rejected at the market (Daniel, 2002: 25). This is because Indonesia is still a price taker in the trade of world cocoa beans and the classic problems that have not been resolved to date are middlemen so that it makes it difficult to increase the income of farmers and cocoa entrepreneurs. Therefore, an alternative solution is needed especially in the current Industrial Revolution 4.0 era.

On the other hand, technological developments that are characterized by easier access to information are increasingly easy, encouraging people to be aware of technology. Even in the millennial era today, the internet and access to social media place themselves as basic needs must be fulfilled by every millennial generation. The data shows that with the population of Indonesia reaching 260 million, the penetration of internet users reached 126 percent or around 371 million. This means that the capacity of internet users is above the overall Indonesian population. 70 million of them are internet users in the form of social media, and 132 million of them are active internet users. (Indef.2017)As a first step to accelerate the development of the cocoa plantation sector in Senara hamlet, it can be done through the Biko.id website. Biko.id is an application website that provides easy marketing for cocoa bean farmers and brown SMEs because people in Senara hamlet are not aware of economic digitization. So that here the author as a young generation will provide assistance to farmers and Brown SMEs in the form of websites and mentoring of course. The development concept of Cocoa Plantation certainly requires a small budget. If we only rely on the local government of North Lombok Regency, NTB, which only

relies on the budget and regional balance, certainly cannot afford to realize the development of the Chocolate Village.

2. Identification of problems

The formulation of the problem that will be concluded :

1. Why is there an urgency to facilitate website access and assistance to farmers?
2. General Description of the Cocoa Business Model (Biko.id) as an initial step for farmers and cocoa businessmen to face the 4.0 Industrial Revolution?

3. Theoretical Commentary

3.1 Understanding Application

Before we discuss further the use of applications as a marketing medium for cocoa beans in increasing the income of farmers and cocoa business people in the village of chocolate senara it would be better to know what the application is. An application is a subclass of computer software that utilizes the ability of the computer directly to perform a task that the user wants. Besides computers, the application is also on a smartphone. Besides that, the application also often means a unit of software that is made to serve the needs of several activities (Berlianty Destiana Tania.2015)

3.2 Understanding Marketing

According to Kotler in Muttaqin (2011: 104) marketing is a social and managerial process where individuals and groups get their needs and desires by creating and offering products that are valuable to others. Modern marketing systems carried out by tourism and non-tourism companies are now utilizing the digital world.

3.3 Understanding Cocoa

Cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.) is one of the leading commodities of the plantation sub-sector. Cocoa commodities consistently act as a source of foreign exchange which contributes very important to the structure of the Indonesian economy (Arsyad et al., 2011). In terms of area, cocoa is the fourth largest for the plantation sub-sector after oil palm, coconut, and rubber. From an economic perspective, cocoa contributes the third largest foreign exchange after palm oil and rubber (Hasibuan et al., 2012).

3.4 Application as a marketing medium

According to Supardi (2009), The benefits and advantages of using e-commerce are media promotion in order to increase sales volume, both for online and conventional sales. In addition to these advantages, it turns out that the results of several studies show that the effectiveness of e-commerce use in boosting the increase in sales volume and promoting industrial products is quite high (Alexander, 2002; Supardi, 2009).

3.5 Industrial Revolution 4.0

The industrial revolution 4.0 is the fourth phase of the history of the industrial revolution that began in the 18th century. According to Prof. Schwab, the world has experienced four industrial

revolutions. The industrial revolution 1.0 was marked by the invention of a steam engine to support production machinery, trains, and sailing ships. Various work tools that originally depended on human and animal power were then replaced by steam engine power. As a result, production can be multiplied and distributed to various regions more massively. However, this industrial revolution also has a negative impact in the form of mass unemployment.

4. Research method

Data collection techniques use two methods, qualitative and quantitative. The qualitative technique is the in-depth interview, where the data comes from the stacking, The Owner Kampung Coklat Senara, the surrounding teenagers or workers in the village of chocolate senara. While quantitative techniques come from online information media. Analysis of business success determinants (CSF) is used to structure the structure of information needs in the management hierarchy. Each manager has specific information needs, is influenced by the level and scale of responsibility, as well as the type and scale of organizational resources that he uses (Witarto, 2004). Key factors of success and inhibitors are the factors that most influence the ability of industry members to succeed in the market. These factors can be in the form of specific elements of the strategy that can be in the form of information resources, information technology system competencies, competition capabilities created by information technology systems that can make the company have a strong position in the market (Jogiyanto, 2005). As for how to calculate weight (weight) based on whether or not the component is important is based on input from the management level. Charging weights follows the following rules: 1 = not important, 2 = less important, 3 = rather important, 4 = important, and 5 = very important. While the method of calculating the rate (rating) based on the frequency of filling in the component is that there are many respondents who choose the "CSF" statement or answer the existence of the component. The filler rate follows the following rules: 1 = a little, 2 = moderate, and 3 = a lot. CSF sequence from the highest point to the lowest point. The type of data used includes primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained through observation, interviews with study objects (community) and The Owner of Kampung Coklat Senara. Secondary data obtained from a variety of credible sources include printed books, journals, and articles, official local and foreign websites, which are then identified, analyzed, and interpreted so that they can be accounted for.

5. Results and discussion

5.1 Urgency to provide easy website access and assistance to farmers in the industrial revolution era 4.0

The availability of a system or proper internet access is not only always the responsibility of the government to intervene to overcome these problems. More than that armed with business creativity and innovation can be done in the era of the digital industry today. One of them is the digital cocoa industry. Moreover, we will enter the industrial revolution era 4.0 where all economic activities must involve internet technology, this is an opportunity to develop the business of farmers and SME actors digitally. The industrial revolution 4.0 opened wide opportunities for anyone to advance. Information technology that is easily accessible to all corners causes everyone to be connected to a social network. Information floods as predicted by Futurologist Alvin Toffler (1970) became a reality found in the current industrial revolution era. This abundant information provides great benefits for the development of science and the economy. One of them in the Senara Chocolate Village is administratively located in Bentek Village, Kayangan District, North Lombok Regency, NTB. Senara Chocolate Village has the potential to develop cocoa beans in today's digital era. A stringed chocolate village was established in March 2018 which can be said as a baby tour, however, in July 2018 it has attracted

160 local and foreign tourists with a total monthly net income of Rp. 5,000,000 and an income of Rp. 5,000,000 / month help the economy of the surrounding community, especially the youth who work in the village of chocolate senara. The natural condition of hilly and natural areas adds to the beauty of the chocolate village. In addition, the Senara Chocolate Village Region has other potentials such as:

1. Senara Chocolate Village

In the vicinity of the chocolate village, Senara has a view of cocoa trees that are no less interesting than other natural attractions in Indonesia. The melodious voice of birds and the natural atmosphere that is still natural. Usually, in the brown canyon area, it is a meeting place for both the government and the private sector while enjoying the chocolate powder processed by the local community.

2. Natural tourism

Around the village area, Senara also provides spots to take pictures with typography of hills that resemble paintings from a distance and added with a beachfront deck of Lombok which is the sweetener and the beautiful Waterfall under the village of Chocolate Senara.

3. Rinjani Mountain

Still from the administrative village of Chocolate Senara, From the Far it we can enjoy the sights of Mount Rinjani. Usually, if you want to see beautiful scenery in the morning, where the view of Mount Rinjani will be decorated by Sunrise from the east

4. Processed variety of ingredients from cocoa beans

After visitors are tired of walking around to see the scenery of the chocolate village and its surroundings. Tourists can enjoy a variety of cooking menus made from cocoa beans, of course in the stalls of the brown village village owned by local residents. The dish feels even more enjoyable watching the views of Mount Rinjani and Lombok Beach from the top of the hill.

5.2 Success Factor Analysis and inhibitors of Senara Chocolate Village Using CSF

CSF or a determinant of success and inhibitor of a business is one of the activities of a company or MSME that has a strong influence on the ability of a company or MSME to achieve its objectives. MSMEs or companies usually have several CSFs. Based on the results of the analysis carried out with the CSF method shows that (1) the existence of an interactive Web can be a marketing development strategy. Score 15. (2) The use of information technology can help MSME management, a score of 12. this shows that the people of the village of chocolate senara especially the owner of the village of chocolate are aware of the importance of using technology as the best promotional media. However, there are still a number of obstacles in the development of the chocolate village tour. From the results; face to face relationship or interviews and observations to chocolate village owners and local residents there are still some obstacles including a) Product, still not optimal processing of cocoa beans and certain tour packages that can accommodate the desires of tourists. In addition, there is no serious attention from the local government to improve the area's natural tourism sector. b) Price, price problems that often occur asymmetric information, because cocoa farmers in the village of Senara still depend on brokers or middlemen so that fraud often occurs by the middlemen making a greater profit margin than the cocoa farmers. c) Place, There is no homestay facility, to support the existence of tourists who want to stay longer. Existing facilities are only a place to sit while enjoying the processed cocoa products manually in berugak like a shelter similar to the rice fields. d) People, the processing

skills of cocoa beans and innovation to process cocoa beans are still very low. Besides that, the skills to manage the village tour of chocolate are still very low. Among them are foreign language skills. However, there is an innovation in the processed industry which is processed by cocoa beans that attract tourists to be used as souvenirs even if processed manually. e) Promotion, not yet formed marketing management parties that promote the Senara Chocolate Village on an ongoing basis. In addition, the use of technology is still limited, both because of the limited provider network coverage and information technology for promotional purposes. Moreover, communication skills in foreign languages are not owned at all. f) The process, Related services to tourists/visitors in order to be in accordance with the standard of chocolate village tourism service or Nature tourism, in general, requires SOP (Standard Operational Procedure). But in reality, there is still no standardization. This becomes very urgent, given that customer satisfaction for service determines tourists to visit again. But the focus of the research of the writer in this research is on promotion issues.

5.3 General Description of the Cocoa Business Model (Biko.id)

Based on the condition of the village of the chocolate village with various kinds of potential that can support the economy of the coastal community, an alternative solution is needed to make it easier for the community and the owner of the chocolate village of skill, capital and the most important thing in digital research. Besides that, the creation of website and marketing applications is intended to provide an understanding of the importance of the concept of digitalization in the industrial revolution era 4.0. thus, if the website and application of BIKO.ID is realized and maximized, it will be able to provide more information to the wider community, both local and foreign, about cocoa products in the village of chocolate senara. server or application creation and biko.id website. This server is in the form of a website that provides explanations related to the biko.id business and provides easy information to people who are interested in cocoa beans, processing results, and chocolate senara village natural attractions. Following is the explanation of the use of the BIKO.ID application. parties who want to order must download the BIKO application at <http://app.appsgeyser.com/7707283/biko>. hope that with the application can help the process of ease of farmers, Bussines Men of cocoa, and lovers of cocoa in the world, especially in Indonesia.

6. Conclusion

Utilization of the application website is intended to prepare farmers and actors in the face of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, where the application website is used as a marketing and ordering medium that is expected to help increase the income of farmers and cocoa businesses, especially in the chocolate village. In the mechanism, media marketing is realized in the form of information on what is the village of chocolate, string, products, tourist spots and lodging in the village of chocolate senara. With Biko.id being an alternative solution to intensify promotion by utilizing the application website and preparing farmers and businesses in the face of competition in the industrial revolution era 4.0. The suggestion that the author will give is the research problem above: Responding to the problems of farmers and cocoa businessmen above, it takes a cross-sector synergy that helps significantly implement Biko.id innovations, among others, the role of students, local governments, academics, the role of universities and the synergy across sectors The authors hope that the Biko.id application website can increase income and be accelerating the development of the chocolate village access so as to help improve the economy of the community in the village of chocolate senara, as well as preparing the public for the current industrial revolution 4.0. and the existence of biko.id helps strengthen partnerships between businesses and cocoa

farmers. It is also hoped that with the existence of biko.id, businesses and cocoa farmers will get capital to develop their businesses.

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